

LEARNER-CENTERED APPROACH IN DEVELOPING INDEPENDENT STUDY SKILLS OF B1 LEARNERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7225283>

Annotation: The author discusses the problems, main principles of speaking skill and show effective strategies to develop it among English language learners based on learner-centered approach taking into consideration their level on this issue. In addition to that, the thesis shows what strategies used to involve students in speaking process during the lesson. The work also shows how to use effective methods and techniques based on learner centered approach in teaching English learners.

Key terms: technique, practice, language philosophy, approach, learner-centered, concept, critical thinking, mind- mapping, visual learning

Introduction

Methods are held to be fixed in teaching systems with prescribed techniques and practices, whereas approaches represent language teaching philosophies that can be interpreted and applied in a variety of different ways in the classroom. Method can be distinguished according to the teaching and learning context and it is used in wide context and narrow context: project work, problem-solving, brainstorming. Approach and method are based on the principles as initial theoretical points.

Thus, principle is an accepted or professed rule of action or conduct. A fundamental, primary, or general law or truth from which others are derived. Ralph W. Emerson said¹: If you learn only methods, you will be tied to your methods. But if you learn principles, you can devise your own methods. The goal of effective teaching is to fundamentally make an impact or change in the learner. Measuring the effectiveness of learning can be demonstrated in a variety of ways, especially in learner-centered learning environments.

Brief review on the related literature

According to Lynch², students should develop their own knowledge by communication, critical thinking, and problem solving; they should have the opportunity to learn in relation to their real life situations in order to use the target language. He claimed that the student' assessment is not based on test and getting average, it is considered as a positive tool to promote and diagnose learning assessment. He summarized student-centered approach into: promoting interaction among learners, using the native language when possible and appropriate, connecting instruction with learners' lives, and teaching learning strategies explicitly. Students learn best when they take ownership of their

¹ Ralph Waldo Emerson, 1811 "The Twelve Principles of Efficiency" economic journal

² cited in Mohammad Zohrabi, Mohammad Ali Torabi&PrivashBaybourdiani, 2012

education and have a role in shaping the instruction. Today's students learn best by doing, and they discover how to learn for themselves in the process. It is here when the impact of effective teaching is most evident, as students who are at the center of their learning will continue their journey with positive lifelong learning skills.

Student-centered learning shifts the balance of classroom power from teacher to student thus fostering active learning and engagement among peers. Student centered learning enables critical thinking and is a means to develop knowledge rather than a collection of facts by building upon and challenging prior learning. Student centered learning situates the teacher as facilitator and contributor rather than authoritarian and director of knowledge. Student centered learning returns the responsibility for learning to the students, so students are able to discover their strengths and weaknesses and take part in directing their own knowledge gain. Student centered learning employs effective assessment to promote learning and inform future practice.

The phrase "learner-centered" is often equated with terms such as "child-centered" or "student-centered". However, "learner-centered" goes beyond that as Lambert and McCombs³ explain: When one examines the learner-centered principles, it is clear that the concept suggests more than that. The principles apply to all of us, cradle to grave, from students in the classroom to teachers, administrators, parents, and others influenced by the process of schooling. Again, we think that's only part of the picture. When one looks across the domains covered in the principles the metacognitive and cognitive, affective, personal and social, developmental, and other individual differences factors, it is clear that there is an emphasis on both the learner and learning. The central understanding that emerges from an integrated and holistic look at the principles, however, is that for educational systems to serve the needs of every learner, it is essential that every instructional decision focus on the individual learner with an understanding of the learning process.

There are lots of techniques and methods which develops speaking skill based on learner-centered approach. For example, cooperative, presentation. KWL, brainstorming, discussion, small group, case study, jigsaw, learning center, role-play, workshop, competition, games, debate, project, demonstration and others. Yet, we can't describe all the methods of learner-centered approach so, taking into consideration the age of B1 learners we have chosen technology of developing "Critical thinking" through reading and writing as a learner-centered approach to develop speaking skill.

Critical thinking is important for students to master because it gives them the skills to "move past the obvious and make individual connections with the text". In social studies classrooms, this means students can analyze different sources of information and facts concerning political and social issues. Certainly, especially

³ McCombs, B. L. & Whisler, J. S. (1989). The role of affective variables in autonomous learning. *Educational Psychologist*, 24(3), 277-306.

for B 1 learners (know the grammar, have vocabulary, can put the words properly in English sentence structure) critical thinking has a great benefit to be successful not only in producing good speech but also a significance in life too.

Involvement of critical thinking skills are the following techniques:

Mind-mapping- the inventor of mind maps is Tony Buzan⁴. With his boundless energy and enthusiasm, he helped millions of people around the world to structure their thoughts, reach their learning goals, and unleash their creativity. Visual thinking, graphical representations and the process of creating diagrams can be traced as far back as the 3rd century. His contribution to the world of visual thinking is immeasurable and we are forever grateful.

Fish bone diagram -the Cause and Effect Diagram (Fish bone Diagram) from Japanese quality control statistician Kaoru Ishikawa is graphical technique that can be used in teams to identify and arrange the causes of an event or problem or outcome. He first used it in 1943 to help explain a project to a group of engineers. It graphically illustrates the hierarchical relationship between the causes according to their level of importance or detail and a given outcome.

Press formula-the technology of reasoned judgment is a pedagogical technique aimed at developing logical argument of students when asked to think of something quickly and with no warning. The PRES formula gets learners to make their arguments by having them express the following: (a) their Point of view; (b) the Reason for their point of view; (c) an Example or Evidence to support their point of view; and (d) to Summarize their point of view

Learner-centered approach activities. Here are some practical ideas for incorporating learner-centered activities into your corporate training:

1. Foster collaboration with group projects

Think of yourself as a coach on the sideline of a sports game. You're offering advice and encouragement where necessary, rather than a lecturer delivering a monologue to learners.

2. Let learners develop content

Start a forum within your LMS or upload podcasts or videos for your learners and let them work individually or in groups to contribute to it. Let them know what topics should be covered and encourage them to research them. Over time, this channel will become a valuable resource for everyone at the organization.

3. Stage presentations

Or, instead of using their research to create different types of media, ask your learners to develop presentations, which can be delivered in-person or via a live webinar (particularly handy for remote teams).

4. Hold a competition

A little healthy competition can really spur motivation in a group.

5. Hold a debate

Split the group in three and give them a motion. One group argues for the motion, one argues against it, and the final group judges. All groups have to stay fully

⁴ Buzan, Tony (1974). Use Your Head. London: BBC Books.

engaged with the topic until the end, and should come out of the debate thoroughly informed on the issue.

6. Gamify learning

Games are a great way to add an element of fun to the learning environment. Gamification has been a huge trend in online learning in recent years. Any good LMS will have gamification features such as leaderboards, badges, points, and more that will encourage learner participation.

7. Pose a problem

Learner-centered approaches work best when your employees feel like they're solving real problems and learning skills they can put to work immediately. As such, you can pose real problems the company is facing and ask your learners to identify creative and innovative solutions.

8. Do role-play

Divide the learners into pairs and let them take turns in the role of the customer. Letting them step into the shoes of your customers is likely to make them more empathetic when they're speaking to them.

9. Brainstorm

Just choose a topic you want your learners to know more about and ask them to volunteer what they already know. As a group, the chances are they know a great deal - and you can fill in any gaps as necessary.

10. Do a demo

Whether you're training on something highly scientific or the ins and outs of new software, showing is often better than telling. Stage a demonstration to show exactly how it works. This can be achieved by uploading a step-by-step video to your LMS.

Conclusion

According to this helpful investigation the state of congruence in learner-centered approach is believed to help with language fluency, as it suggests that developing critical thinking via modeling such as mind-mapping, fish-bone, press formula produces better language speaking results. During my research work, I found out teaching speaking to B1 learners has a great responsibility as well as challenges. Because your job is not controlling their speech, instructing right, checking their grammar and vocabulary, but also we should motivate them and take into consideration each learners' character as they are teenager and have much difficulties with their character and behavior. From the thesis, it can be concluded that the most important peculiarity of teaching speaking are related to directing learners to do modelling of their speech. In this field our research work has faced with several methods, techniques, games, advantages and disadvantages to have a speaking lesson based on learner-centered approach. We found out that the most effective way to have a good lesson is the technology "Critical thinking". It is appropriate for B1 learners level and it is interesting for them unlike traditional

method. Moreover, it shows positive effect on learners' psychology and personality. Although they make any grammar or vocabulary mistakes on their speech, they feel confident themselves for they have a "map" for speech and don't stop making speech.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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